

THE MAIN PROBLEMS OF MORAL AND SPIRITUAL EDUCATION OF YOUTH GENERATION

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the relevance of spiritual education in the conditions of the new Uzbekistan. The role of the views of the medieval Eastern thinkers Beruni and Ibn Sino in the education of youth is revealed. Special attention is paid to the historical and philosophical interpretation of the idea of the perfect man in the works of thinkers. The idea of the perfect man in the creative heritage of thinkers in the upbringing of the perfect generation in the conditions of the new Uzbekistan is important.*

Keywords: *renaissance, new Uzbekistan, thinkers of the medieval East, spirituality, education.*

INTRODUCTION. At the celebrations on the occasion of the 29th anniversary of Independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the words of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan were heard: “currently, the foundation of a new renaissance is being laid in Uzbekistan – the third Renaissance” [1]. It should be noted that the processes of recovery currently taking place in all spheres of our life are showing their importance for health. Therefore, if in the early years of our independence we aspired to national identity, understanding the true meaning of our rich historical, spiritual and scientific heritage and its realization, now our people have gradually begun to realize the idea of “from national revival to national uplift.” During this period, there was a tendency in our society to raise public thinking, and the inherent embodiment of both national and universal values was recognized.

In his speech at the “teacher and mentor Day”, the head of our state noted: “We set the issue of the third Renaissance as a strategic task and raise it to the level of a national idea. We consider preschool and school education, the system of higher and secondary special education, scientific and cultural institutions as four inseparable rings of the coming Renaissance. And we consider kindergarten teachers, school teachers, teachers and the scientific and creative intelligentsia to be the four pillars of the new Renaissance. I believe that dear parents will definitely support this initiative and become the fifth ring, the fifth pillar of the new renaissance.”

LITERATURE REVIEW

The works of thinkers of the medieval East serve as a theoretical and methodological source, a guide for research. The research was based on such methods of scientific cognition as dialectics, historicism, logic, analysis and synthesis, and an integrated approach.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

As recognized by the entire world community, Uzbekistan has been the cornerstone of culture and civilization since time immemorial. Indeed, the scientific and spiritual achievements that arose on the territory of Uzbekistan in the Middle Ages became the basis of science in Europe. The incomparable scientific and philosophical treatises of our great thinkers, such as Muhammad al-Khorezmi, Abu Ali ibn Sina, Abu Rayhan Beruni, Abu Nasr Farabi, along with the development

and systematization of secular knowledge laid the foundation for the rise of the universal tamadduni, relating not only to his time, but also to subsequent centuries.

The main problems of moral and spiritual education of young people.

- Insufficient attention from parents and teachers. The lack of proper attention and care from adults can lead to the fact that young people will not receive the necessary moral and spiritual education.
- Exposure to negative patterns and values from the environment. Young people can be influenced by aggressive and unacceptable culture, media education, violence and even extremism, which can greatly affect their worldview and values.
- Lack of spiritual foundations and traditions. Many young people lose touch with spiritual traditions and values, which can lead to a lack of a moral compass and a lack of spiritual orientation.
- Riots and lawlessness in society. Violations of laws, corruption and injustice in society can set a bad example for young people and lead to the spread of criminal activity.
- Lack of follow-up guidance and support. Many young people may have difficulty finding their place in society and need guidance and support to develop their moral and spiritual qualities.

The great thinker Abu Rayhan Beruni justified such methods as matching education with character, soft principles of teaching and upbringing. In the knowledge of nature and society, he followed the motto: "Without checking myself, I will not believe."

As an experienced teacher, he has developed a number of recommendations on teaching skills. For example, the art of teaching everything, matching the character, taking into account the characteristics of children, etc. Beruni wrote: "The goal is not to prolong time, but to avoid monotony. Because looking at the same things for a long time leads to fatigue and kills patience. Periodically changing the types of the subject, the student will feel himself in different gardens, which one reveals their charms to the other. Each new one inspires the student and it helps to improve memory." He condemned simple memorization in the learning process and insisted that memorization should be combined with understanding. "A lot of observations help to develop the ability to remember a lot. "Beruni wrote in his book "Osoral — bokiya": "Having gathered all my strength, having done everything possible, that is; sometimes having heard, sometimes having seen and compared, I decided to state what I know" and dreamed that all teachers would have the same qualities.

The scientist and philosopher Abu Ali ibn Sina in his works "The Place of the Event" and "The Canon of Medical Science" wrote about his views on pedagogical skills. For example, when working with children, the teacher must be smart, healthy, and emphasizes the need for professionalism.

Ibn Sina in his work "The Canon of Morality" revealed the causes of negative and positive qualities in the general features of a person's character. The scientist in this work states that positive and negative qualities arise from habit and under the influence of the state nobility. Ibn Sina in his works gives an explanation of such concepts as: justice, generosity, patience, responsibility, loyalty, composure, modesty and other qualities. A learned man, he believed, should be clean in all respects and treat others in a polite manner. He considered it especially important to renounce the pleasures of life in favor of himself. Ibn Sina's views are reflected in his main works: The Canon of Medical Science and Kitob al-Shifo. Ibn Sina explains such positive qualities as justice, cleanliness, complacency and also reveals negative flaws such as fear, hypocrisy, avarice, theft,

fraud, "Courage manifests itself in human actions. Patience is the energy that holds back trouble so that a person can get out of this situation. Sensitivity is an energy that helps you quickly realize the meaning of what is happening," he explains in his works.

CONCLUSION

Today, the state has set a task to prepare a completely new generation: an active, inquisitive one. In general, the spiritual and moral development and upbringing of a person is a complex and multifaceted process. It is inseparable from human life in its entirety and inconsistency, from society, culture, family and humanity as a whole, as well as from the country of residence and the cultural and historical epoch that forms the way of life of the people, as well as human consciousness. It is extremely important to create a well-functioning system of spiritual and moral education in preschool educational institutions based on the values of traditional spiritual culture.

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